

Proposing a new method for creating integer weights for Iterative Proportional Fittings based on locally calibrated model

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Summary

Iterative proportional fitting is one of the methods for Spatial Microsimulation and synthetic population estimation. Albeit the simplicity and speed of computation, the technique results in non-integer weights for individual rows of data. To solve this issue, different integerisation methods were proposed for the past decade to transform the continuous weight variable into a discrete number of unique individuals. However, little work has been done to find out how much error and bias is introduced by integerisation. In this research paper, we present new method for creating integer weights based on locally calibrated model. The results are encouraging; however, it needs further testing and validation.

KEYWORDS: Synthetic population estimation, Integer Conversion, Iterative Proportional Fittings, Spatial Heterogeneity, Spatial Microsimulation

1. Introduction

The synthetic population has been a standard approach to help understand and estimate the aggregate behaviour of large numbers of individuals. This results in a demand for spatial microsimulation that provides an estimation of the detailed individual behaviours at the small-area level which is often not available to academics due to confidentiality and collection difficulties. One of the ways that researchers can implement spatial microsimulation is in the form of iterative proportional fittings (IPF) that reweigh a non-geographical population micro-data set to fit small area descriptions without stochastic process (Lovell and Ballas, 2013).

Nevertheless, the use of IPF is susceptible to spatial heterogeneity. The deterministic reweighing approach by IPF assumes that all zones within the specific region are homogeneous, however, there is always some degree of heterogeneity with the fine level of spatial granularity (Voas and Williamson, 2000; Bowman, 2004). Such heterogeneity problem can cause many problems such as inconsistency of table totals/marginals and biased tables, and thus need integer conversion (Choupani and Mamdoohi, 2016). Although people have used Monte Carlo simulation to minimise the sensitivity of the IPF estimators, there are few applications and theoretical explanation in the field of spatial sciences. Consequently, in line with what Smith et al (2009) propose as ways to bring the place into spatial microsimulation, local models should be calibrated by using regionally specific orders of variables.

Our research is designed to extend the current understanding of spatial microsimulation. Aiming to further understand the implications of the patterns of integerisation and spatial weighting to each individual according to the heterogeneous nature of small-level areas' attributes. We conduct experiments using different constraint configurations with permutations for building accurate synthetic micro-populations based on 2011 Living Costs and Food Survey. The final results show that by using

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a locally calibrated simulation, we find a new opportunity of adjusting for area-specific characteristics as an updated method for integer conversion; we can significantly improve the accuracy of the population simulation process.

2. Methods

2.1 Rationale

One of the main criticisms of IPF is that IPF results in fractional weights instead of integer populations which handles small geographical areas poorly. There have been two arguments regarding this issue. On the one hand, as suggested by Williamson et al. (1998), we should use an alternative spatial microsimulation method based on random sampling and optimisation techniques such as “combinatorial optimisation microsimulation”. However, it can be computationally intensive (Pritchard & Miller, 2012). On the other hand, we should improve the methods of avoiding using the fractional weight (Ballas et al., 2005a).

Despite the importance of integral weights for dynamic spatial microsimulation, there has been little work directed towards integerisation. Little work has been done to find out how much error is introduced and the theoretical explanation of why the error occurs (Guo and Bhat, 2007; Voas and Williamson, 2000). The main challenge is that treating fractional weight as a rounding problem assumes that all zones within the specific region are homogenous, however, there is always some degree of heterogeneity that necessitates the evolution of synthesis in heterogeneous zones.

One way to overcome this limitation is to use a multilevel IPF, which incorporates both individual and neighbourhood benchmarks (Fenton, 2016). Bar-Gera et al. (2009) and Muller and Axhausen (2011) present a new opportunity with an entropy-based optimization model in which each neighbourhood is assigned a weight by the entropy function that is defined in terms of both individual and household weights. My speculation is that not all geographical areas should have the same chance of receiving the compensatory values, as it will, therefore, assume all the areas have the same attributes. We could not find any references in the literature on the use of spatial entropy sequences of population synthesis, and so decide to investigate the suitability of locally calibrated algorithms to adjust the probability of which each geographical area should receive a compensatory value, using locally derived weights. We could not find any references in the literature on the use of spatial entropy sequences for population synthesis, and so decide to investigate the suitability of locally calibrated algorithms to adjust the probability of which each geographical area should receive a compensatory value, using local derived weights.

2.2 The Proposed Algorithm: A Hybrid Multilevel IPF Model with Spatial Heterogeneity

The problems associated with the aforementioned integerisation strategies demonstrate the need for an alternative method. Ideally, the method would capture not only individuals/household weighting, but extend to a spatial and neighbourhood variant. A hybrid multilevel IPF model draws inspiration from Bar-Gera et al. (2009), Lovelace and Ballas (2013) and Fenton (2016). Different orders of constraint variables could be defined for each regional sub-sample, type of neighbourhoods or rural versus urban areas. Their application suggests that this may reflect local specificities better. We adjust their models for unobserved regional effects by incorporating the different permutation possibilities and find the set with the minimal TAE. This paper attempted a new entropy-based optimisation based on spatial heterogeneity of the permutation that adjusts the probability of which cells should receive compensatory values.

3. The test scenario: input data and IPF

To test the proposed algorithm, we further extend the example proposed by James et al (2019), which they presented new GIS datasets of household expenditure across Great Britain. To ensure that we can cross-validate the proposed algorithm, we control the same dataset and method as suggested by the article to allow their respective performance characteristics to be quantified and compared. They conducted an iterative proportional fittings framework to model the weekly household's expenditure such as alcohol, tobacco and cigarettes, and socio-demographic characteristics of economically active individuals in the UK. The characteristics of these individuals were simulated by reweighting a synthetic micro dataset based on aggregate constraint variables provided at the Local Authority District area (LA) level. The synthetic micro dataset was created by a subset Living Cost and Food Survey (LCF), covering approximately 12,000 respondents from 6,000 households each year from 2009-2018.

In this case study, we extracted the 2406 respondents from 933 households in London for the year 2011 to cross-validate with the 2011 census data. The baseline population is based on data from the Office for National Statistics mid-year population estimates (ONS, 2011). IPF was used to assign 71 weights to each of the 4933 individuals, one weight for each zone and the process is repeated until an adequate level of convergence is attained, with the weights were set to an initial value of one. The weights were then iteratively altered to match the aggregate (LAD) level statistics for each constraint variables. The final synthetic population was produced using both 'Truncate, replicate, sample' (TRS) and locally calibrated methods to estimate LAD level estimates of expenditure by category.

4. Results

Figure 1 shows an example of how the locally calibrated model can be applied. In contrary to the model proposed by James et al (2019), we found a slightly different result. In our algorithms which we have applied the spatial weighting method, we found there is a similar pattern between weekly alcohol and tobacco expenditure. However, for miscellaneous goods, our results demonstrate a totally different spatial pattern from alcohol and tobacco consumption which is in line with the conceptual reasoning. Our findings differentiate the previous literature where they did not explicitly distinguish the pattern differences between alcohol, tobacco and miscellaneous products.

In addition, our result found a smaller total absolute error (TAE) of the variables of interest by comparing the proposed algorithm and TRS suggested by Lovelace and Ballas (2013). We also explored the spatial differences of TAE which is computed by TRS and found there is a clear spatial concentration through mapping. In order to mitigate the issues of spatial heterogeneity, we should bring local specificities in the spatial microsimulation model. We used integer conversion to avoid further distortion caused by the spatial distribution which presents a new window for theorising the integral rounding method. However, we do not know the correlation between constraint variables in the census and simulated data which requires further validation.

Figure 1. Estimated average weekly expenditure per person for 2011 in London.‡

‡ **Skav**: weekly average smoking expenditure **Alav**: weekly average alcohol expenditure

Miav: weekly average miscellaneous goods expenditure **TAE**: Total absolute error

5. Conclusions and future work

This paper explores an attempt to incorporate the spatial function to minimise the TAE in consideration of the spatial heterogeneity. I have done the second step of the proposed algorithm on the living cost and food survey data. Whilst this study focuses on Great Britain, the framework here could be applied to any location with the appropriate data sources. Whilst this paper has discussed simulated estimates at the level of large local authorities, there is considerable interest in and effort towards simulation and estimation at yet smaller spatial scales.

For each regional sub-sample, specific order of constraint variables could be specified. However, the idea of integer conversion is still untested. Thus, with further tuning and adaptation, we might use the evaluation matrix as suggested by Lovelace and Ballas (2013), which they used four different performance indicators sample size, TAE of simulated areas, anomalies (aggregate cell values out by more than 5%) and correlation between constraint variables in the census and microstimulated data that compare across other integerisation method.

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Biographies

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